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REFLEXIONS ON THE COMPARISON OF IDT DATA SETS

by L Lindegren

Perryman's comparison of the RGO and CSS analyses of simulation run 9 (1986 June 2; RGO Workshop Sept 21-22) nicely demonstrates the power of graphical presentations in revealing unexpected relations and discrepancies (e.g. the strange behaviour of I_0^* and I_1^* for faint stars, and the anomalous F5 values for certain observations). The presence of outliers (due to phase ambiguity or bugs in either analysis program) is no problem in a graphical comparison, whereas any numerical comparison would have to take rather elaborate precautions against them. Numerical methods are still needed, however, in order to get a quantitative answer to the main question: how close are the two analyses?

The current format for the reduced data (Appendix I in Perryman's paper) contains essentially six different data types:

1. Frame#, star#, number of samples, true phase (P_{true}), photometric data (B, B-V) and approximate grid coordinates (scanfield indices G, H)
Comment: There is no reason why these should not be identical between the two (or more) reductions. If they are not, the reason should be identified and the software corrected.
2. Intensities ($I_0, I_1, I_2, I_0^*, I_1^*$)
Comment: Within each magnitude class, graphical comparison is probably best and perhaps also sufficient. For a larger magnitude range, a plot of $2.5 \lg [I_0(\text{RGO})/I_0(\text{CSS})]$ etc versus magnitude is probably useful.
3. Phases (p_1, p_2, p^*)
Comment: In any comparison, phase ambiguity should be removed by replacing the 'raw' phase differences $\Delta p_1 = p_1(\text{RGO}) - p_1(\text{CSS or TRUE})$ and $\Delta p_2 = p_2(\text{RGO}) - p_2(\dots)$ with the modified differences

$$\Delta \tilde{p}_1 = \Delta p_1 - s * \text{ANINT}(\Delta p_1 / s), \quad \Delta \tilde{p}_2 = \Delta p_2 - h * \text{ANINT}(\Delta p_2 / h)$$

where $s = 1.208''$, $h = s/2$. However, even after this precaution, the mean and rms phase differences should be computed by some robust algorithm rejecting outliers (see below).

4. Mean errors (σ_{I_0} , σ_{I_1} , σ_{I_2} , $\sigma_{I_0^*}$, $\sigma_{I_1^*}$, σ_{p_1} , σ_{p_2} , σ_{p^*})

Comment: Mean errors are always positive and tend to have approximately constant relative uncertainties. This suggests that it is better to compare (graphically or numerically) $\lg(\sigma)$ than σ .

5. Normalized errors (e_1 , e_2 , e^*)

Comment: The normalized phase errors, $e_i = (p_i - P_{\text{true}})/\sigma_i$, are intended as internal test statistics for the 'normalcy' of the reduction, viz. that the results are unbiased, approximately normal, and the standard deviation^{as} indicated by the formal mean errors. It does not make much sense to compare e 's from two different reductions, since it would not be clear if the differences depend on the phase estimates or the formal mean errors. Since e is expected to follow a normal distribution with zero mean and unit variance, the most comprehensive result is a normal probability plot of the e 's (separately for each reduction and each magnitude interval). No numerical comparison is needed above that.

6. Test statistics (F5, T2, F35)

Comment: Graphical comparison only.

When computing the mean and standard deviation of a sample expected to be almost normal, one should use an algorithm which is insensitive to outliers i.e. gross deviations from the expected distribution. Such deviations may be due to program bugs, and it is usually better to have them pointed out separately and rejected in the calculation of the sample mean and standard deviation. Typically, points beyond a certain multiple of the standard deviation are rejected and the process iterated till it converges. The rejection limit should be adjusted according to the number of points. An example of such an algorithm is shown on the last page.

When the errors of the phase estimates become comparable to one radian (192 mas for the first harmonic, 96 mas for the second), one cannot expect a normal distribution any longer; the tails of the distribution blend with the phase ambiguity problem and the extreme result is a uniform distribution:

of all phases. For the faint stars in Run 9 the rms error of the second harmonic phase is just about 1 radian, and a comparison in terms of mean and rms differences starts to become meaningless. In the following I propose an additional measure of the 'distance' between two reductions of the same photon counts, which does not suffer from phase ambiguity and which would even work in the absence of modulation.

The new measure Q is computed in terms of the ordinary Fourier coefficients b_1 to b_5 defined by:

$$N_\ell \sim b_1 + b_2 \cos H_\ell + b_3 \sin H_\ell + b_4 \cos 2H_\ell + b_5 \sin 2H_\ell \quad (1)$$

where N_ℓ is the number of counts in sample ℓ and H_ℓ is a suitable reference phase. These are obtained from the usual parameters as:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} b_1 &= I_0 \Delta t &= I_0^* \Delta t \\ b_2 &= I_1 \cos(2\pi p_1/s) \Delta t &= I_1^* \cos(2\pi p^*/s) \Delta t \\ b_3 &= -I_1 \sin(2\pi p_1/s) \Delta t &= -I_1^* \sin(2\pi p^*/s) \Delta t \\ b_4 &= I_2 \cos(4\pi p_2/s) \Delta t &= R I_1^* \cos(4\pi p^*/s) \Delta t \\ b_5 &= -I_2 \sin(4\pi p_2/s) \Delta t &= -R I_1^* \sin(4\pi p^*/s) \Delta t \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

(five parameter fit) (three parameter fit)

where $t = 1/1200$ s, $s = 1.208''$, and R is the value for M_2/M_1 used in the three-parameter reduction (can be assumed to be the true average ratio).

Let $\hat{b}_A$ and $\hat{b}_B$ be the estimates of $\underline{b} = (b_1, b_2, \dots, b_5)$ resulting from two reductions (RGO and CSS, for instance), and $\Delta \underline{b} = \hat{b}_A - \hat{b}_B$. Then

$$Q = \left[\frac{n}{5b_1} (\Delta b_1)^2 + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=2}^5 \Delta b_i^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (3)$$

should be $\ll 1$ if the difference between the two reductions is small compared to the statistical uncertainties. Here, b_1 is either of the values $\hat{b}_{1A}$ or $\hat{b}_{1B}$ (they are normally very close to each other) and n is the number of accepted samples.

The rationale for this measure of distance is as follows. The standard deviation of (1), regarded as an observation equation for $\underline{b}$, is the square root of the left-hand side (according to Poisson statistics), or approxi-

mately $\sqrt{b_1}$ (if we neglect the modulation). Forming the normal equations for $\underline{b}$ in the usual manner, using equal weighting, we find that the covariance of the least-squares estimate $\hat{\underline{b}}$ is approximately

$$\underline{C} = (b_1/n) \text{diag}(1, 2, 2, 2, 2) \quad (4)$$

Thus if, for the moment, $\Delta\underline{b} = \hat{\underline{b}} - \underline{b}_{\text{true}}$ is the difference between the estimate and the true vector, then

$$5Q^2 = \Delta\underline{b}' \underline{C}^{-1} \Delta\underline{b} \quad (5)$$

should have the chi-square distribution with 5 degrees of freedom and Q should be of the order of unity. The measure Q can be interpreted as the 'size' of any vector difference $\Delta\underline{b}$ in units of the statistical errors of the estimate.

It is interesting that Q can also be written

$$Q = \left(\frac{n}{5 \langle I \rangle} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \langle (I_A - I_B)^2 \rangle^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (6)$$

where $I_A(t)$, $I_B(t)$ are the 'light curves' in counts per second fitted in the two reductions. Thus, Q is proportional to the rms difference between the light curves.

For the first four observations reproduced in Appendix II of Perryman's note, the following Q values were found for the difference between the RGO and the CSS reductions:

frame 1, star 56, $Q = 0.126$ (bright)
 frame 1, star 55, $Q = 0.059$ (faint)
 frame 1, star 54, $Q = 0.123$ (bright)
 frame -1, star 719, $Q = 0.157$ (bright)

```

c*****
c SUBROUTINE trim(n, x, ave, sd, nout, iout)
c*****
c This routine calculates a trimmed sample mean and standard deviation
c by iteratively rejecting points more than w times the standard
c deviation from the mean. w is a function of the number of points
c (n), w = sqrt(2*log(n)). For a normal population, the expected
c number of points beyond this limit is about 0.3. The number of
c points rejected and their indices in the data array are
c also returned.
c
c The algorithm requires n > 5 (approx) to be able to detect one
c outlier, and n > 7 to detect two outliers. For large n, it can
c accommodate at least 20% outliers.

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c L Lindsgren 1986 Oct 02

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c INPUT:
c n = number of data points (unchanged on exit)
c x(1:n) = array of data points (unchanged on exit)
c
c OUTPUT:
c ave = mean of the retained data points
c sd = sample standard deviation of the retained points
c nout = number of points rejected
c iout(1:nout) = indices of rejected points in the input array x
c
c In the calling program, x() and iout() should be dimensioned
c to a length .GE. n.

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DIMENSION x(n), iout(n)
IF (n .LE. 0) RETURN
w = sqrt(2.*alog(float(n)))
iter = 0
maxit = 20
nout = 0

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c Determine the sample mean and s.d. without rejection:

```

ave = 0.
DO 10 i = 1, n
ave = ave + x(i)
10 CONTINUE
ave = ave/float(n)
sd = 0.
DO 20 i = 1, n
sd = sd + (x(i) - ave)**2
20 CONTINUE
IF (n .LE. 1) RETURN
sd = sqrt(sd/float(n-1))
IF (n .LE. 2) RETURN

```

c Main iteration loop starts hereafter:

c 100 CONTINUE

```

xlim = w*sd
nout = 0
ave1 = 0.
sd1 = 0.
DO 110 i = 1, n
dx = x(i) - ave
IF (abs(dx) .LE. xlim) THEN
ave1 = ave1 + x(i)
sd1 = sd1 + dx**2
ELSE
nout = nout + 1
iout(nout) = i
ENDIF
110 CONTINUE
nin = n - nout
ave1 = ave1/float(nin)
sd1 = sqrt((sd1 - float(nin)*(ave1-ave)**2)/float(nin-1))
IF (ave1 .NE. ave .AND. iter .LE. maxit) THEN
ave = ave1
sd = sd1
iter = iter + 1
GOTO 100
ENDIF
RETURN
END

```